

ANALYSIS OF AGILE GOVERNANCE MODELS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PUBLIC SERVICES IN THE FIELD OF POPULATION ADMINISTRATION IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

This article discusses best practice research in the administration of public services in the field of population administration at the Department of Population and Civil Registration of the Surabaya City Government. This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study research design. Data mining was carried out by in-depth interviews with four informants consisting of leaders and employees. The results of the study identify six new variables for the governance of public service delivery, namely 1) Excellence Governance is the governance of public service providers that carry out excellence, 2) Business Process Based On Software is the activity of the process of providing public services based on software and technology, 3) Society Participation is to provide space for the community to participate in the governance of public service delivery, 4) Employee Motivation is the spirit of employees in providing quality public services to the community, 5) Adaptive Approach is the ability of the governance of public service providers to respond to changes quickly and systematically, 6) Service Design is the ability of public service providers to design public service procedures that are easy and in accordance with community expectations. Best practice in the administration of public services in the field of population administration at the Department of Population and Civil Registration of the Surabaya City Government is expected to be adopted by the Population and Civil Registration Office of other City or Regency governments in Indonesia.

Keywords: Public Service, Agile Governance, Population Administration

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of technology requires the government to be more responsive, adaptive and innovative to changes in order to provide excellent public services to the community. The use of information and communication technology is a medium for moderating the relationship between citizen satisfaction and the government through access to public services (Abdulkareem & Ramli, 2021). Research on public service so far can be divided into two main trends. First, research that analyzes Public Service Motivation (PSM) which generally discusses an employee having motivation in providing public services (Wright et al., 2017), (Liu et al., 2018), (Kim, 2018), (Ward, 2019), (Budiyanti et al., 2019), Second, research that looks at the organization of public service providers in providing public services (Tuurnas, 2015), (Klierova & Kutik, 2017), (Negoita, 2018), (Pesti & Randma-Liiv, 2018). In essence, there are various approaches that have been applied to research public services. The results of these studies are generally not much different, that employee motivation in providing public services is still lacking. The organization also has difficulty controlling the opportunistic behavior of employees in providing public services.

Public service research in a modern administrative approach accommodates the dynamic atmosphere of globalization because it uses a multi-dimensional and disciplined approach in analyzing interrelated internal and external areas. One of the modern administrative approaches is to use an agile governance approach which captures the organization's ability to respond quickly to unexpected changes in meeting the demands and needs of an increasingly changing society (Holmqvist, 2014). Agile governance emerges within the realm of organization and encourages people to apply agile organizational governance to improve process performance and organizational productivity (Luna et al., 2014). In addition, agile governance is also defined as the organization's ability to be able to perform cost efficiency, as well as increase the speed and accuracy in exploiting opportunities to make innovative and competitive actions. (Huang & Pan, 2014), (Liang et al., 2017).

Research (Luna, Kruchten & Moura, 2015) regarding agile governance can be realized in the future if the government can apply six principles in the administration of agile government, namely: 1) Good enough governance is that the level of governance must always be adjusted to the organizational context, 2) Business-driven is that business must be the reason for every decision and action. , 3) Human focused, namely that the community must be respected and given space to participate in governance, 4) Based on quick wins, successes achieved quickly must be celebrated and used as motivation to get more stimulation and results. 5) Systematic and Adaptive approach, namely the team must be able to develop intrinsic capabilities to be able to respond to changes quickly and systematically, 6) Simple design and continuous refinement, namely the team must be able to provide fast results and always improve. (Luna, Kruchten & Moura, 2015).

This is in line with the views of Schwab, Klaus and David which he wrote in a book entitled *Shaping The Future of The Fourth Industrial Revolution – A Guide to Building A Better World*, see that in implementing agile government the government must apply an agile governance approach strategy, namely (1) creating a policy laboratory, (2) encouraging collaboration, (3) supporting crowdsourcing policies (4) developing a private regulator ecosystem, (5) principles innovation, (6) integration of public engagement, (7) supporting the role of global organizational bodies in providing oversight, (8) technological approaches, (9) responding to change (Schawb, 2018).

Luna, 2015 in a study on Agile Government Theory: conceptual development also synthesizes approaches agile governance and conventional governance, as table 1.

Table 1 : Agile Governance Value

No	Agile Governance	Conventional Governance
1	It's more about behavior and practice... than...	... processes and procedures
2	It's more about achieving sustainability and competitiveness... than about	... audited and complied
3	It's more about transparency and community engagement for business... than...	...monitor and control
4	It's more about reasoning, adapting and responding... than about	...following the plan

Source: (Luna, Kruchten & Moura, 2015)

Through the concept of agile governance, the government is triggered to think ahead in order to understand future situations that will affect the government through a responsive and adaptive conceptualization process to protect the people from the threats and challenges of new conditions that exist. Policies need to be adapted to accommodate current and long-term community needs. The concept of agile governance defines the ability of the government's learning process to think about achieving sustainable success by responding to changes quickly and systematically. Agile governance focuses more on responsive, adaptive and innovative governance processes, then allows the government to take agile policies in the face of future changes to improve the efficiency of public services and public welfare.

The current public policies of the central government and local governments that are responsive, adaptive and innovative can give prominent meaning to the regional autonomy agenda which is still a challenge to be realized. Based on initial observations and reports in various media, there are several regions in Indonesia that have produced policies that seem to favor the people.

The Surabaya City Government produces policies on public service innovations that favor the community, namely the “Cak Emus” it means Cangkrukan Entrepreneur Muda Surabaya, for which this program received an award in the Public Service Innovation System from the Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform in 2019. Previously in 2018 the Surabaya City Government had also received 3 (three) programs received an award in the Public Service Innovation System from the Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform namely innovation “TAHU PANAS” (Tak Takut Kehujan, Tak Takut Kepanasan) is an activity to repair uninhabitable houses through a social rehabilitation program for slum areas, a public service innovation unit from the Surabaya City Government Social Service. Furthermore, the City Development Planning Agency of the Surabaya City Government with its innovations, namely Economic Heroes and Young Fighters. This innovation is focused on empowering housewives from poor families and young fighters. The goal of the economic hero is to reduce the poor to get out of the shackles of poverty. Meanwhile, the Young Fighters are intended for young people who drop out of school or do not continue at the tertiary level, but still have the will for better economic access. (Announcement of Top 99 Public Service Innovations of KEMENPAN-RB)

The third innovation in 2018 is the 6 in 1 public service innovation which includes the management of birth certificates, death, marriage, divorce, moving letters coming and moving out online at the Department of Population and Civil Registration of the Surabaya City Government. The 6 in 1 innovation was initiated to reduce the volume of queues for requests for public services at the Population and Civil Registration Office, and brokers who open up illegal levies, as well as reduce the processing time of files, so that people can take care of them without having to come to the Population and Registration Office. Civil service, but only with the e-Lampid application, the public can immediately take care of public services in the field of administration including the processing of birth certificates, deaths, marriages, divorces, letters of moving in and out. (Announcement of Top 99 Public Service Innovations of KEMENPAN-RB). The purpose of this study is to identify the process of providing public services in the field of population administration services using the agile governance model at the Department of Population and Civil Registration of the Surabaya City Government.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Public Service Implementation

A service is an activity or a series of activities that behave invisibly that occurs as a result of interactions between customers and employees or other conditions carried out by the service donor industry which is intended to uncover customer or client cases”(Gronroos, 1990) Public design, the majority is considered from a private point of view, meaning that the public is interpreted as a realm that lies outside the achievements that are transacted by individuals. In everyday life, we have been accustomed to think of the state as a representation of public needs. In conclusion, the management of public services is simplified into "services provided by the state through its bureaucracy" (Lay,2002). After that (Subarsono, 2005) describes: “Public services are a series of activities attempted by the public bureaucracy to fulfill the wishes of the public as consumers. Consumers or clients are defined here as citizens who want public services, such as making Identity Cards, Birth Certificates, Marriage Certificates, Death Certificates, Land Certificates, Business Permits, Building Permits, Disturbance Permits, Underground Water Intake Permits, Drinking Water Subscriptions. , Electricity, and the like”.

In the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25 of 2009 concerning public services, it is stated that "public service is an activity or arrangement of activities in terms of the need for services that are suitable/in accordance with the laws and regulations for every citizen and society for goods, services, and or or administrative services provided by the executor of public services. The organization of public service delivery is also defined in Article 8 of Law Number 25 of 2009, at least includes: a) Service implementation; b) Management of public complaints; c) Information management; d) Internal control; e) Counseling to the community; and f) Consulting services.

Agile

Agile history by (Agile manifesto, n.d.) Agile methods emerged when seventeen entrepreneurs met on February 11-13, 2001, at The Lodge at Snowbird ski resort in the Wasatch mountains of Utah. The seventeen people tried to find common ground how a technology must always evolve, so at the meeting the emergence of an agile manifesto concept 'software development' extreme programming development, SCRUM, DSDM, adaptive software development, crystal, feature-based development, pragmatic programming, and others according to the need for alternatives to the documentation process.

The seventeen people call themselves the 'agile alliance' groups of independent thinkers on software development and sometimes compete with each other. While the manifesto provided some specific ideas, Bob Martin made the statement that we are all honored to work with a group of people who hold a compatible set of values, a set of values based on trust and mutual respect, and promote an organizational model based on people, collaboration, and type building. -the type of community organization in which we want to work. At its core, I believe Agile Methodology is really about "soft" stuff - about delivering great products to clients by working in areas that are nothing more than dialogue about "people as heritage especially us" but actually "role" as if the very meaningful, and run out of "relic" speech. So in the final analysis, the growing interest in and sometimes overwhelming criticism of Agile Methodology is about the softness of values and culture.

For example, I think that in the end, Extreme Programming has mushroomed in use and interest, not because of pair programming or refactoring, but because, as a whole, the practice defines a developer community that is freed from the burden of Dilbertesque corporations. Kent Beck tells of an early job where he estimated six weeks of programming effort for two people. After his manager reassigned another programmer at the start of the project, he finished the project in twelve weeks and felt bad about himself! The boss of course commented on Kent about how slow he was for the second six weeks. Kent, somewhat saddened that he "failed" like a programmer, eventually realized that his initial six-week estimate was very accurate for two and that his "failure" was really the manager's failure, indeed, the failure of the standard "fixed" process mindset so often. infect our industry.

This type of situation occurs every day marketing, or management, or external customers, internal customers, and even developers do not want to make hard trade-off decisions, so they impose irrational demands through the imposition of the company, the power structure. This is not just a software development issue, it runs throughout the Dilbertesque organization.

To succeed in the new economy, to move aggressively into the age of e-business, e-commerce, and the web, companies must disengage themselves from their Dilbert manifestations of mysterious and work-making policies. This freedom from the vagaries of corporate life attracts supporters of Agile Methodology, and scares the begehers (you can't use the word 'unlucky' in a professional paper) from traditionalists. Honestly, Agile comes close to scaring off corporate bureaucrats at least those who like to push process by process

versus trying to do what's best for the "customer" and deliver something that's timely and tangible and "as promised" because they've run out of places to hide.

The Agile movement is not anti-methodology, in fact, many of us want to restore credibility to the word methodology. We want to restore balance. We embrace modeling, but not to submit multiple charts in dusty industrial repositories. We embrace selection, but not hundreds of pages of thick novels that have never been maintained and are not used often. We design, but identify programming limits within the overflow area. Those who would call proponents of XP or SCRUM or any of the other Agile Methodologies "hackers" are ignorant of the methodology and original definition of the term hacker. (Agile manifesto, n.d.)

The literal meaning of agile is "being able to move quickly and easily", in terms of agile software development it will mean a "flexible" process to respond to changes quickly (Hardik, 2019). Agile is a strategy for managing software maintenance and support activities (Hardik, 2019) like kanban this agile methodology has been (and continues to be) successfully used by thousands of organizations around the world (Agile manifesto, n.d.) especially in the United States and Europe. Some of the more prominent organizations using the Agile Methodology include Nokia Siemens Networks, Yahoo, Google, Microsoft, BT, Bankwest and SunCorp.

As for the values and principles in agile methodology, there are 4 (four) values as shown in Figure 1 and 12 (twelve) principles as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1 : Agile Values

Agile Values (from the Agile Manifesto)

The **Agile Manifesto** establishes a set of **four values** that are **people-centric** and **results-driven**:

That is, while there is value in the items on the right, we value the items on the left *more*.

Source: (Hardik, 2019)

Figure 2 : Agile Principles

12 Agile Princiles

Source : (Hardik, 2019)

(Hardik, 2019)states an agile model for improving software (systems) in the development cycle. The system development life cycle (SDLC) is a series of stages or phases that provide a systematic model for the creation and management of software applications. In addition, as a systems analyst,(Hardik, 2019)make detailed plans after problem analysis, solution requirements analysis and design analysis before software development processes such as implementation, testing, maintenance and replacement will take place.

Agile Governance

In various studies, agile governance appears in the organizational area and encourages people to apply agile organizational governance to improve process performance and organizational productivity(Luna et al., 2014). Agile Governance is defined as the organization's ability to respond quickly to unexpected changes in meeting the demands and needs of an increasingly changing society(Holmqvist, 2014). In addition, Agile Governance is also defined as the organization's ability to be able to carry out cost efficiency, as well as increase speed and

accuracy in exploiting opportunities to make innovative and competitive actions. (Huang & Pan, 2014), (Liang et al., 2017).

Alexandre J. H. de O. Luna, Philippe Kruchten, Hermano P. de Moura wrote an article entitled Agile Governance Theory: conceptual development. The results of the study built a conceptual framework from Theory of Agile Governance, namely 1) Good enough governance is the level of governance must always be adjusted to the organizational context, 2) Business-driven is that business must be the reason for every decision and action, 3) Human focused is the community must be respected and given space to participate in governance, 4) Based on quick wins, successes that are achieved quickly must be celebrated and used as motivation to get more stimulation and results. 5) Systematic and Adaptive approach, namely the team must be able to develop intrinsic capabilities to be able to respond to changes quickly and systematically, 6) Simple design and continuous refinement, namely the team must be able to provide fast results and always improve.(Luna, Kruchten & Moura, 2015). Luna, Kruchten and Moura, building Agile Governance theory into these six principles, is an approach for research or practice of agile governance in the future.

This is in line with the views of Schawb, Klaus and David which he wrote in a book entitled Shaping The Future of The Fourth Industrial Revolution – A Guide to Building A Better World which sees that in implementing an agile government the government must apply an agile governance approach strategy, namely (1) create a policy laboratory, (2) encourage collaboration, (3) support crowdsourcing policies (4) development of a private regulatory ecosystem, (5) innovation principles, (6) integration of public involvement, (7) support the role of global organizational bodies in provide oversight, (8) technological approach, (9) respond to change(Schawb, 2018).

METHODS

This research was conducted at the Department of Population and Civil Registration Surabaya City Government through a qualitative approach, the research design is a case study in accordance with the main questions regarding how (Creswell, 2010)Whereas case study research is designed for studies that are used to answer phenomena, by developing an in-depth analysis of a program or process. The focus of this research is the identification of the process of providing public services in the field of population administration services using the agile governance model at the Department of Population and Civil Registration of the Surabaya City Government.

The method of extracting data is carried out by studying literature and in-depth interviews with informants who have been determined based on the consideration that informants can provide data information needed in research. The use of a qualitative approach in this research is also based on the description (Guba, 1985) Qualitative research or naturalistic inquiry is a research method that is intended to understand evidence, social reality, and the assumptions of existing people. Refers also to thoughts for(Nasution, 2003) If qualitative research or naturalistic research is carried out in an atmosphere of facts in the research field

that is "natural" or natural as it is, without being manipulated and regulated through any experimentation.

In this study, in-depth interviews were conducted with four informants who were familiar with the data sought by the researcher. Interviews were conducted directly with informants at the Office of Population and Civil Registration, each interviewing researchers guided by questions that had been prepared by researchers that were semi-structured and open. Each question will always be developed based on new information obtained from the informant during the interview. Researchers conducted redundancies for interview results that did not match the focus data of this study by coding based on the research focus.

RESULTS

The results of the analysis of the data collected based on in-depth interviews were categorized into six identification variables, namely Excellence Governance, Business Process Based On Software, Society Participation, Employee Motivation, Adaptive Approach, Service Design.

Table 2: Participant's profile

Participant ID	Gender	Age	Position*
1	Female	41-50	Top
2	Female	41-50	Middle
3	Female	31-40	Middle
4	Male	31-40	Middle

*Top refers to the higher-level leadership positions; Middle refers to the middle-level leadership positions department of population and civil registration.

Excellence Governance

Is the governance of public service providers that carry out governance excellence in providing quality public services. The interview excerpt from the informant was stated by (P1).

"The value applied by the Surabaya City Population and Civil Registration Service is to provide fast and appropriate services to the community, besides that the Head of the Service always reminds that "work is at the same time worship"

In addition, other informants stated that governance excellence is how an organization is able to formulate a vision and mission and how to realize that vision. The following is an excerpt from the interview by (P2).

"The vision and mission of the organization will reflect the big goals to be achieved by the organization, so if the organization wants to carry out excellent governance, the organization must first know the major achievements that the organization wants to achieve by formulating the VISION and MISSION"

The Vision, Mission and Motto of the Surabaya City Government Population and Civil Registration Service are: Vision: Information Technology-Based Population Administration

Services 2016-2021, Mission: Realizing Population Administration Services with Information Technology-Based Population Databases, Motto: Population and Civil Registration Services are increasingly easy and close to the community.

This is in line with what was stated that the excellent governance that forms the basis for the implementation of public services carried out by the Department of Population and Civil Registration is fast and accurate service to the community. Expressed by (P3).

"The values that we always emphasize are providing fast and precise service to the community, so we always think about how to provide services to the community so that they are satisfied with the excellent governance approach".

Business Process Based On Software

Utilization of technology applications in business processes for every decision and action in the implementation of public services. Department of Population and Civil Registration in every process to provide services to the community by utilizing technology, as stated by (P4).

"The Department of Population and Civil Registration always uses technology in providing public services to the community, by utilizing technology the service will be faster, people can provide services online"

The Department of Population and Civil Registration always provides public service innovations to improve the quality of services to the community, stated by (P1).

"The Department of Population and Civil Registration always thinks how to improve the quality of service to the community, we always make innovations in the provision of public services including the E-Klamping 6 in 1, the Kalimasada Village Program, the Mobile Service Car Program (Jempol Sekti), and media information about administration population through the SWARGALOKA youtube channel"

The innovations made by the Department of Population and Civil Registration are not only limited to service innovations for managing population administration, but also for service complaints against services obtained by the community, stated by (P3).

"The Department of Population and Civil Registration opens all online and offline access for the public to be able to freely provide suggestions and input offline, the public can come directly to the office, while online can be through the omni channel, a complaint system that is always connected to several complaints access either from social media, call center, e-mail and greeting applications"

Society Participation

The public is given space to participate in the governance of public service delivery, starting at the planning, implementation, and evaluation stages of public service standards. as stated by (P1).

"The community is always given space to participate in the implementation of public services, because this has also been mandated by law that in the preparation of public service standards must involve elements of the community"

The mechanism for community involvement in the preparation of standards as stated by (P3).

"The community mechanism in the involvement of standard setting is by providing direct input when we socialize the draft of public service standards that we have formulated based on regulations, and the results of the evaluation of the implementation of public services so far"

There are several ways of outreach to the community to get input on the draft standard that has been formulated in several ways as stated by (P4).

"Direct socialization to the community, through leaflets, through the website of the Population and Civil Registration Service, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, Podcasts, as well as hierarchically through sub-districts, villages in their respective regions, as well as through Cak Ning Minduk cadres"

Furthermore, for community involvement in the implementation and evaluation stages of the implementation of public services as stated by (P2).

"The community provides services in accordance with the service standards set by the Population and Civil Registration Service, at the implementation stage if the community feels that the service is not in line with their expectations, they will directly evaluate it by providing criticism and suggestions"

Employee Motivation

Activities carried out by employees in providing quality public services to the community, as stated by (P1).

"All employees of the Department of Population and Civil Registration are always motivated to provide quality public services to the community, employees are always evaluated by the leadership based on their performance and the results of criticism and suggestions from the community"

In addition, so that employees are always motivated in providing public services to the community, the Department of Population and Civil Registration also always provides training to employees, as stated by (P2).

"To improve the competence of all employees, the Department of Population and Civil Registration often provides training to employees, such as understanding of regulatory changes, understanding of team work, understanding of service quality, technology skills, so that employees are also motivated to provide excellent service to the community"

Then the existence of sanctions or employee performance evaluations also makes employees always motivated to provide excellent service to the community, stated by (P3).

"That every weekend the leadership always evaluates the performance of employees in providing services to the community, so that with this evaluation employees must achieve their performance in providing public services to the community, this is also a motivating factor for employees in providing excellent service to the community"

Adaptive Approach

The ability of public service providers to be able to respond to changes quickly and systematically is a principle held by the Department of Population and Civil Registration, as stated by (P1).

"We, the Department of Population and Civil Registration always have an Adaptive Approach principle to respond to changes, especially changes in technology; almost all public services that we organize are based on technology, online services do not have to come directly to the Department of Population and Civil Registration"

This is in line with what was conveyed by (P2).

"We are always adaptive to changes, changes in regulations or changes in technology. In changing technology, we use it to provide fast and appropriate services, such as our public service innovation, namely E-Klampid"

The Department of Population and Civil Registration in providing services always uses technology to provide service satisfaction for the community. As submitted by (P4).

"With the rapid development of technology, people's demands for fast public services have become a challenge for us in providing services, so we always use technology in providing services to the community online such as Birth Certificates, Death Certificates, Moving Out Letters, Transfer Letters Come, Application for Marriage and Application for Divorce"

Service Design

The ability of public service providers to design service delivery mechanisms in accordance with community expectations based on the evaluation results from community suggestions, as submitted by (P1).

"We make public service procedures in accordance with regulations and input from the community, so what we do is design service procedures, disseminate service procedures to the community, implement service procedures, evaluate service procedures, design new service procedures. Such a cycle is what we always do in making service procedures, so it is hoped that these service procedures are in accordance with the expectations of the community"

Public service procedures at the Department of Population and Civil Registration, the service process is made simple, as stated by (P3).

"We make the procedure for providing public services simple with the hope that it will be easy for people to get public services from us, we provide public services online, so people don't have to come to the office to get public services, just from home they can also get public services from the Population Service and Civil Registration"

For people who cannot use technology or provide online services, they will be assisted by the Population Administration Cadre in the Village. As stated by (P2).

"So we from the Department of Population and Civil Registration have population administration cadres who have the task of conducting outreach to the public to be aware of the importance of population administration, besides that it is also our duty to help people who have not been able to use online services, so that all people will be able to get public services from the Department of Population and Civil Registration"

The Department of Population and Civil Registration makes an easy service design, so that all levels of society can perform and receive services from the Department of Population and Civil Registration.

DISCUSSION

The rapid development of technology requires the government to be more responsive, adaptive and innovative to changes in order to provide excellent public services to the community. The concept of agile governance offers responsive, adaptive and innovative governance as a form of providing excellent public services to the community. The implementation of public services at the Department of Population and Civil Registration of the Surabaya City Government in providing public services to the community always uses technology to make innovations in public services, E-Klampid Innovation is a 6 in 1 service innovation which includes the management of birth certificates, deaths, marriages, divorces , moving letters come in and move out online.

The Department of Population and Civil Registration in the implementation of public services always has the principle of excellence governance to carry out superior organizational governance by setting the vision and mission of the organization as the basis for the implementation of public service delivery which are the values and principles of all employees to provide fast and appropriate services to the community. This is in line with the findings (Holmqvist, 2014)that the organization must be able to respond quickly to unexpected changes in order to meet the demands and needs of an increasingly changing society,(Huang & Pan, 2014), (Liang et al., 2017)states that the organization's ability to be able to perform cost efficiency, as well as increase the speed and accuracy in exploiting opportunities to make innovative and competitive actions.(Schawb, 2018)stated that in the administration of government there must be a policy laboratory focused on policies to always provide excellent service.

In providing public services, the Department of Population and Civil Registration utilizes technology applications in business processes for every decision and action in the administration of public services. Public services are carried out online, the process of

complaints from the public is also carried out online with the Omni channel program, and public service innovations are made based on technology. Community involvement in the governance of public service delivery at the Population and Civil Registration Service is carried out at the planning, implementation and evaluation stages. At the planning stage, the community is involved in the process of preparing public service standards which will later become standards in the implementation of public service delivery, at the implementation stage the community provides services while monitoring and evaluating the services they receive, which then if the community feels dissatisfied with their services, the community will provide services. Criticism and suggestions to the Department of Population and Civil Registration. These criticisms and suggestions are used as evaluation material for the Department of Population and Civil Registration to create new designs for public service standards. This is in line with the findings (Luna, Kruchten & Moura, 2015) that in governance must respect and provide space for public participation in the implementation of public services.

As for the motivation of employees of the Population and Civil Registration Service in providing public services to the community, they have high motivation they always work with the principle of providing satisfaction to the people who receive services, the Population and Civil Registration Service also always provides training to improve employee capabilities, especially related to changes in regulations and skills in using technology in the delivery of public services. In addition, the Department of Population and Civil Registration is always adaptive to technological changes, the Department of Population and Civil Registration responds to changes quickly to make public service innovations to increase public satisfaction with fast and accurate services through online services. This is in line with the findings (Luna, Kruchten & Moura, 2015) that the success achieved quickly should be used as motivation to get more stimulation and results. Besides that (Luna, Kruchten & Moura, 2015) states that the team must be able to develop the intrinsic ability to be able to respond to change quickly and systematically.

The Department of Population and Civil Registration designs a service delivery mechanism in accordance with the expectations of the community through several stages, including starting with designing service procedures, disseminating service procedures to the community, implementing service procedures, evaluating service procedures, and designing new service procedures. Such a cycle is always carried out by the Department of Population and Civil Registration in making service procedures, so that the service procedures are in accordance with the expectations of the community.

CONCLUSION

Best practice research on the implementation of public services in the field of population administration at the Department of Population and Civil Registration of the Surabaya City Government with an agile governance approach can identify six new variables in the findings of this study. The Department of Population and Civil Registration in the implementation of public services has the concept that in organizational governance, especially in the provision

of public services, it must have the principles of 1) Excellence Governance is the governance of public service providers that carry out excellence, 2) Business Process Based On Software is the activity of the implementation process public services based on software and technology, 3) Society Participation is to provide public space to participate in the governance of public service delivery, 4) Employee Motivation is the spirit of employees in providing quality public services to the community, 5) Adaptive Approach is the ability to manage organizations providing public services in responding to changes quickly and systematically, 6) Service Design is the ability of organizations providing public services to design public service procedures that are easy and in line with public expectations.

PRACTICE IMPLICATIONS

The Department of Population and Civil Registration of the Surabaya City Government in the implementation of public services has a vision of fast and precise service and provides excellent service for community satisfaction with the principles of public service delivery: Excellence Governance, Business Process Based on Software, Society Participation, Employee Motivation, Adaptive Approach, Service design. Best practice in the administration of public services in the field of population administration at the Department of Population and Civil Registration of the Surabaya City Government is expected to be adopted by the Population and Civil Registration Office of other City or Regency governments in Indonesia.

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